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Mulching Material and Growing Season Effect on the Expression of Agromorphological Traits of Onion (*Allium Cepa* L.) Variety ARES in Korhogo, North of Côte d'Ivoire

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Received Date: 5-Sep-2022

Accepted Date: 12-Oct-2022

Published Date: 31-Oct-2022

Abstract

Côte d'Ivoire is not self-sufficient in onion. To make it autonomous, one of the solutions would be to provide farmers the appropriate varieties with an optimal cultural technique. It is in this perspective that this study has been conducted. Its objective is to evaluate the agromorphological performance of onion variety ARES in rainy and dry seasons with two mulching materials (Rice bran and plastic mulch). In this study, Karibou, dry season onion variety, has been used as control. The number of plants was 100 per variety on a usable area (S²) of 1.40 m² for a bed. The results of the work revealed that the rice bran mulch has a positive effect on agromorphological characteristics compared to the plastic bag mulch and the non-mulch control. With rice bran mulch, the average mass of the bulbs has been 77.82g. The beds with plastic bag mulch and those without mulch registered the respective overage of 42.75 and 47.17 g. The beds with rice bran mulch had the highest bulb yields of 7.20 kg/S² (51 tons per hectare), followed by the plants without mulch which averaged 4.35 kg/S² (31 tons per hectare). The lowest yield has been obtained with the bagged mulch plants, which provided an average of 3.95 kg/S² wether 28 tons per hectare. During the rainy and dry seasons, the variety ARES performed better than the control. These performances are statically identic during the both seasons. The mass of the bulbs fluctuates between 66.60 and 77.82 g when the bulb yield varied between 44 and 51 tons per hectare. With regard to its performances, the variety ARES can be advised for the culture in any season with the rice bran mulch. The culture of this variety can be extended to different agro-climates.

Keywords: Onion, Variety ARES, Mulching, Agromorphological performances, Côte d'Ivoire

INTRODUCTION

Onion (*Allium cepa* L) is a biennial herbaceous plant species. It is grown for its bulbs of strong flavor and smell or for its leaves and presents good economic prospects. Onion is one of the most traded raw vegetables in the world due to its relatively long shelf life (D'alessandro and Soumah, 2008). In 2012, the worldwide onion production was 82,850,000 tons per year, with 56,730,000 tons per year for Asia. The worldwide onion production in 2019, was 9.90,106 tons, with 66.30,106 tons for Asia (FAOSTAT, 2019a). This makes onion the second most important horticultural product after tomatoes. More than 175 countries produce onions on approximately 3.6 million hectares of cultivable land (D'alessandro and Soumah, 2008).

In Africa, onion is also an important product for many countries. This includes Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Chad, Côte D'Ivoire, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Mali, Mauritania, Niger and Senegal. According to FAOSTAT (2019b), the global production of onion in Africa is estimated at 5.3 million tons.

In Western Africa, onion is fluently consumed and represents 10-25% of vegetable consumption (Dupaigne *et al.*, 2006). The annual average of onion production, estimated at 1.1 million tons, represents less than 2% of the worldwide onion production. The utmost producer in West African region is Nigeria. It is also the utmost net importer because of its large population, which consumes the country's entire annual production

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estimated at 618,000 tons (Nana, 2016). Niger, is considered as the first and the most important producer in the WAEMU space with a production of 447,000 tons in 2008 (Nana, 2016). In terms of export, Niger and Burkina Faso are the only two countries in Western Africa that produce onions in sufficient quantity to satisfy the domestic demand and to export their surplus (D'alessandro and Soumah, 2008).

In Côte d'Ivoire, the growth of onion imports has always been strong compared to national production which has remained very low. In 2018, with a production estimated between 5,000 and 8,000 tons, Côte d'Ivoire remains one of the smallest onion producer in the sub-region despite a significant potential of production in both, savanna and forest areas (RONGEAD, 2014). In 2013, onion was the third most imported foodstuff by Côte d'Ivoire after rice and wheat. With an annual onion average consumption probably most elevated estimated between 4 and 5 kg/person, Côte d'Ivoire absorbs between 7,000 and 8,000 tons of onion per month. The consumption in urban areas is estimated between 6 and 8 kg/year/person, whether a level closed to that of the main large african cities, while it is on average less than 2 kg/year/person in rural areas (RONGEAD, 2014). The onion sector, therefore appears as a sector with a strong unexploited potential and an important lever for economic and social development to improve the incomes of the producers. It helps to limit inflation on consumer prices and improve the balance of foreign trade balance of Côte d'Ivoire (RONGEAD, 2014).

Onions are generally grown in the dry season in Côte d'Ivoire. This leads to a shortage of Ivorian onions on the national market after the rainy season. To remedy this situation, it is necessary to encourage the cultivation of rainy season varieties. It is in this perspective that the variety ARES was experimented in order to appreciate its agronomic potentials. The general objective of this study is to make Côte d'Ivoire self-sufficient in onion through the improvement of the production of different varieties. Specifically, the aim is to know the agromorphological performance of the variety ARES Compared to different mulches and the growing season in order to provide farmers an optimal cultural technique.

2- MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1- Study site

The study has been carried out on the experimental site of the University Peleforo Gon Coulibaly of Korhogo (UPGC) (Figure 1). The town of Korhogo is located in the north of Côte d'Ivoire. The department is located between 5°16 and 16°16 west longitude and 8°32 and 10°20 north latitude. The climate is the tropical Sudanese-Guinean type, marked by two major seasons, a rainy season that extends from May to October and a dry season from November to April (Boko-Koiadia *et al.* 2016).

2.2- Materials

2.2.1- Plant material

The plant material is consisted of the onion variety ARES. The variety KARIBOU has been used as control. The variety KARIBOU in fact, has been identified by Koffi *et al.* (2022) as one of the best dry season onion varieties.

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Figure 1: Map of Korhogo locality locating the study area

2.3 Methods

2.3.1. Experimental device

2.3.1.1. Sowing in nursery

The nursery of the rainy season has been established in late March 2020 and the nursery of the dry season in mid-November 2020. Onion seeds have been sown in well plate at a rate of three seeds per hole as recommended by Koffi *et al.* (2021) (Figure 2). The substrate used was the potting soil. Water has been supplied twice a day, morning and evening. The Seed plot has been conducted under a shade house.

2.3.1.2- Setting up of the test

A staking and preparation of the beds has been carried out on account of 3 m × 1 m × 15 cm (L × W × H) whether 3 m² on a height of 15 cm. The beds have been hoed and levelled.

Fertilization, consisted of a contribution of mineral and organic fertilizer three days before transplanting. Two hundred grams (200 g) of mineral fertilizer NPK15 15 15 and nine kilograms (09 kg) of compost have been applied per bed followed by watering of the beds. The mulching of the beds with plastics and rice bran has then been carried out.

After forty (40) days in the seed plot, the plants have been transported in the alveolates until the plot for the planting. The test has been conducted in the rainy and dry seasons.

The experimental device in the field consisted of two (02) blocks. Each block consisted of three plots and on each plot, the varieties ARES and KARIBOU have been transplanted (Figure 3). In each block, two beds received mulch treatments (Figure 4). The third bed without mulch has been used as control (Figure 5). The plants were transplanted on the beds with a spacing of 15 cm between rows and 10 cm between the plants. The number of plants was 100 per variety on a usable area (S²) of 1.40 m² for a bed.

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Figure 2 : Seven days old onion plants in nursery

Figure 3: Experimental design

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Figure 3 : The mulches used as treatment (A : Plastic Mulch ; B : Rice Bran Mulch)

Figure 4 : Control without mulch

2.3.1.3- Data collection methods

The morphological and agronomic data collected and the methods are recorded in the Table 1. These datas have been collected on 30 plants randomly selected by variety and by bed.

Table 1: Descriptors and methods of collection of agro-morphological traits of quantitatives type in two varieties of onion

Quantitative Morphological Traits (SI Unit)	Codes	Methods Of Measure
Plant's height (Cm)	PH	The measuret is made from the collar to the top of the longest leaf. The measure is made on the 60th day after planting (DAR). The average plants height has been calculated from the datas of thirty (30) plants measured per variety per bed (Figure 6).
Number of leaves per plant	NL	All the leaves including terminal buds are counted 60 days after planting (DAR)
Maximum length of leaves (cm)	MLL	The measure is made on the longest leaf 60 days after planting (DAR). It has been carried out with a tape measure in centimetres (cm) and was done from the base to the top of the leaf.

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Maximum diameter of the leaves (cm)	MDL	The diameter was measured on the longest leaf and at its widest point (Figure 6). These data have been collected 60 days after planting (DAR).
Weight of the bulbs (g)	WB	For the different characteristics of the bulbs, an electronic balance with a precision of 0.01 g has been used (Figure 7).
Length of the bulbs (cm)	LB	This variable has been measured using vernier caliper (Figure 8).
Diameter of the bulbs (Cm)	DB	Measured using a vernier caliper (Figure 8).
Bulbs Yield (Kg/Area (S ²))	BY	For this trait, the yield of each variety has been obtained according to the treatments, by weighing the mass of the bulbs collected on the surface of the elementary plot, which is 1.4 m ² (S ²).

Figure 6: Measure the height and maximum diameter of the leaf

Figure 7 : Measure of the mass of the bulbs

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Figure 8: Measure of the diameter and the length of the bulbs

2.3.1.5. Statistical analysis of the datas

Statistical analyses have been carried out using SPSS version 22 software. The overage values and standard deviations of the collected datas have been calculated for each descriptor. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) incorporating the Newman and Keuls post ANOVA test has been performed to compare the effects of the different mulch treatments.

Student's t-test has been used to compare the agromorphological performance of the variety ARES to the control. It has also been used to assess the effects of the seasons on the agromorphological characteristics of ARES

3- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3-1. Results

3.1.1. Effect of the mulch treatment on the expression of the different traits studied

The average values and standard deviations of the variables are grouped in the Table 2. For most of the traits measured, the plants with the treatment « rice bran mulch » had significantly the highest values.

Plants with the treatment «rice bran mulch » recorded an average of 51.01 ± 7.23 cm for the heigth and produced more leaves (08.28). For these same traits, the plants in the non-mulch beds recorded average heights of 44.40 ± 7.37 cm and produced around 07.40 leaves. The plants in the bag mulch treatments obtained a height of 44.40 ± 7.37 cm and produced 06.98 leaves.

The rice bran mulch method significantly influenced the mass of the bulbs with an average of 77.82 g. This is higher than the average of the other methods, which recorded respectively the averages of 42.75 and 47.17 g for the bagged and unmulched beds.

The plants with rice bran mulch had the highest bulb yields of 7.20 kg/S^2 (51 tonnes per hectare), followed by the plants without mulch which averaged 4.35 kg/S^2 (31 tonnes per hectare). The lowest yield has been obtained with the bagged mulch plants which provided an average of 3.95 kg/S^2 whether 28 tonnes per hectare.

Table 2: Effect of different mulches on the expression of agromorphological traits of the onion variety ARES

Traits	Treatments			F	P
	Bagged Mulch	Rice Bran Mulch	Without Mulch		
PH (cm)	$34,54 \pm 5,43c$	$51,01 \pm 7,23a$	$44,40 \pm 7,37b$	60,663	0,001
NL	$06,98 \pm 1,07c$	$08,28 \pm 1,81a$	$07,40 \pm 1,21b$	08,919	0,001
MPL (cm)	$31,46 \pm 5,29c$	$45,63 \pm 6,80a$	$39,18 \pm 6,26b$	53,224	0,001
MDL (cm)	$01,28 \pm 0,25b$	$01,53 \pm 0,35a$	$01,69 \pm 0,25a$	20,542	0,001
BM (g)	$42,75 \pm 14,79c$	$77,82 \pm 43,30a$	$47,17 \pm 19,67b$	17,653	0,001
LB (cm)	$04,07 \pm 6,03c$	$04,55 \pm 6,18a$	$04,13 \pm 5,19a$	8,350	0,001

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DB (cm)	04,58 ± 8,18b	05,37 ± 12,85a	04,41 ± 9,91b	9,651	0,001
YB (kg/S ²)	03,95 ± 0,98c	07,20 ± 2,86a	04,35 ± 1,30b	17,653	0,001

NB: Values with the same letters are statistically identical at 5% threshold according to the Newman and Keuls Test.

PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves per plant; MPL: Maximum plant length; MDL: Maximum diameter of the leaf; BM: Bulb mass; LB: Length of each bulb; DB: Diameter of each bulb; YB: Yield of each bulb. F: Statistical value of the test, p: Probability value of the test.

3.1.2. Comparisons of the variety ARES to the control

In the rainy season, except the diameter of bulbs (DB), the variety ARES had the best agromorphological performances compared to the control (Table 3). In this period, the variety ARES produced heavier onion bulbs with an average of 77.82 g. The yield for the area used has been 7.20 ± 2.86 kg/S² whether an equivalent around 51 tonnes per hectare. For the same traits, the control had values of 20.64 g for bulb mass and 1.90 kg/S² equivalent around 14 tonnes per hectare for yield.

The average values and the standard deviations of the traits in dry season are grouped in Table 4. Except for the trait maximum diameter of the leaves (MDL), the variety ARES is significantly different from the control. ARES recorded an average of mass of 66.60 g for the bulbs. The control recorded an average of 50.73 g. The bulb yield has been of 06.22 ± 1.18 kg/S² whether 44 tonnes per hectare for the variety ARES. The yield of the control has been 04.59 ± 1.32 kg/S² whether 33 tonnes per hectare.

Table 3: Comparison of the performances of the variety ARES with the control in the rainy season

Descriptors	ARES in rainy season	KARIBOU in rainy season	t	p
	Average ± Standard Deviation	Average ± Standard Deviation		
PH (cm)	51,01 ± 7,23a	27,37 ± 3,30b	14,317	0,001
NL	08,28 ± 1,81a	06,20 ± 1,64b	7,855	0,001
MPL (cm)	45,63 ± 6,80a	25,10 ± 3,28b	13,999	0,001
MDL (cm)	01,53 ± 0,35ab	01,17 ± 0,09ab	5,623	0,001
BM (g)	77,82 ± 43,30a	20,64 ± 9,40b	5,623	0,001
LB (cm)	04,55 ± 6,18a	2,81 ± 1,35b	10,899	0,001
DB (cm)	05,37 ± 12,85a	3,39 ± 05,16b	1,753	0,085
YB (kg/S ²)	07,20 ± 2,86a	01,90 ± 0,62b	5,623	0,001

PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves per plant; MPL: Maximum plant length; MDL: Maximum diameter of the leaf; BM: Bulb mass; LB: Length of each bulb; DB: Diameter of each bulb; NSB: Number of scales of each bulb; TSB: Thickness of scales of each bulb; YB: Yield of each bulb, T: Statistical value of the test, p: Probability value of the test.

Table 4: Comparison of the performances of the variety ARES with the control in dry season.

Descriptors	ARES in dry season	KARIBOU in dry season	t	P
	Average ± Standard Deviation	Average ± Standard Deviation		
PH (cm)	51,23 ± 6,32a	43,03 ± 6,09b	-5,117	0,001
NL	09,63 ± 2,46a	07,57 ± 2,34b	-3,334	0,001
MPL (cm)	47,93 ± 5,92a	40,70 ± 5,80b	-4,778	0,001
MDL (cm)	01,45 ± 0,74b	02,44 ± 6,34a	0,849	0,399

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BM (g)	66,60 ± 17,59a	50,73 ± 18,83b	-3,373	0,001
LB (cm)	05,57 ± 0,48a	04,11 ± 0,57b	-10,715	0,001
DB (cm)	05,05 ± 0,66a	04,65 ± 0,76b	-2,154	0,035
YB (kg/S ²)	06,22 ± 1,18a	04,59 ± 1,32b	-3,555	0,001

PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves per plant; MPL: Maximum plant length; MDL: Maximum diameter of the leaf; BM: Bulb mass; LB: Length of each bulb; DB: Diameter of each bulb; NSB: Number of scales of each bulb; TSB: Thickness of scales of each bulb; YB: Yield of each bulb. t: Statistical value of the test, p: Probability value of the test.

3.1.3- Effect of the seasons on the expression of agromorphological traits of the variety ARES

The results show that except for the number of leaves (NL) and the length of each bulb (LB), the agromorphological performances of the variety ARES have been stable during the both seasons (Table 5).

During the both seasons, there is no significant differences between the bulb weights (66.60 ± 17.59 and 77.82 ± 43.30 g) as well as the yield which is 6.22 ± 1.18 kg/S² (44 tonnes per hectare) in the dry season and 7.20 ± 2.86 kg/S² (51 tonnes per hectare) in the rainy season.

Table 5: Comparison of the performances of the variety ARES in the dry and rainy seasons.

Descriptors	ARES in dry season	ARES in rainy season	t	P
	Average ± Standard Deviation			
PH (cm)	51,23 ± 6,32 a	51,01 ± 7,23 a	-0,136	0,892
NL	9,63 ± 2,46 a	8,28 ± 1,81 b	-2,553	0,014
MPL (cm)	47,93 ± 5,92 a	45,63 ± 6,80 a	-1,514	0,135
MDL (cm)	1,45 ± 0,74 a	1,53 ± 0,35 a	0,511	0,612
BM (g)	66,60 ± 17,59 a	77,82 ± 43,30 a	1,337	0,186
LB (cm)	5,57 ± 0,48 a	4,55 ± 0,62 b	-7,784	0,001
DB (cm)	5,05 ± 0,66 a	6,43 ± 6,72 a	1,294	0,203
YB (kg/S ²)	6,22 ± 1,18 a	7,20 ± 2,86 a	1,259	0,212

PH: Plant height; NL: Number of leaves per plant; MPL: Maximum plant length; MDL: Maximum diameter of the leaf; BM: Bulb mass; LB: Length of each bulb; DB: Diameter of each bulb; NSB: Number of scales of each bulb; TSB: Thickness of scales of each bulb; YB: Yield of each bulb. t: Statistical value of the test, p: Probability value of the test.

3.2- DISCUSSION

This study has been initiated to assess the expression of agromorphological traits of the onion variety ARES in relation to different cultural practices. The rice bran mulch used in this test allowed the plants to express the best of their genetic potential. With this mulch, the bulbs are more developed and the yield is higher. Rice bran, which is organic material, would contribute to the enrichment of the soil and provides plants mineral elements that are essential for their development (Alium *et al.* 2021, Sawadogo *et al.* 2022). The rice bran is rich in potassium, phosphorus, calcium and magnesium (Bhosale and Vijayalakshmi, 2015; Mas'ud *et al.*, 2017; Liboga *et al.*, 2019).

In contrast to the rice bran mulch, the bagged mulch gave the lowest values of the measured traits. Although this mulch prevents weediness better (Fortier *et al.* 2020), it does not facilitate hoeing operations, which are essential in the cultivation of onion (Bello *et al.* 2019). For years now, agronomic studies show that the use of plastic mulch can lead to a certain degradation of quality of the agricultural soils (Fortier *et al.* 2020). The bagged mulch would increase the amount of heat in the soil, which can be detrimental to plant development. Regardless of the treatments applied, the variety ARES performed better than the control in both the rainy and dry seasons. ARES is a variety resulting from a research programme especially designed for the rainy season. Indeed, since several years, selectors work to create varieties that allow producers to sell their bulbs

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in the off-season when there are no more onions on the market. Thus ARES, because of its vigour, presents an excellent capacity to withstand rainy season growing conditions.

Furthermore, this study showed a stability of the agromorphological characteristics of the variety ARES in the rainy and dry seasons. This indicates that this variety could adapt to several ecological conditions. The performance of the variety ARES compared to variety Karibou in the dry season supports this hypothesis. Indeed, Karibou has been identified by some authors as one of the best dry season varieties (Koffi *et al.* 2022).

The high bulb yields of the variety ARES during the both seasons would be due to the development of its vegetative traits, notably the vigour, the number and development of its leaves. In this study the values of the traits leaf of ARES have been higher than those of Karibou. The developed leaves provide plants a large leaf area and have a positive effect on the yield (Goulet-Fortin, 2009). The leaves through their photosynthetic activity contribute significantly to the improvement of the fruit production in plants (Harou, 2018). Moreover, the result of interactions between the traits of a variety, the factors and conditions of the environment it exploits and the modifications it undergoes through cultural techniques determines the yield. The variety ARES would fit better in the growing conditions in this study.

4. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

This study has been conducted to investigate the effects of the growing season and the mulch on the agromorphological characteristics of the onion variety ARES.

The results of the work revealed that rice bran mulch has a positive effect on the agromorphological characteristics compared to plastic bag mulch and non-mulch control. With rice bran mulch, the average mass of the bulbs has been 77.82 g. The bagged and unmulched beds recorded the respective averages of 42.75 and 47.17 g. The beds with rice bran mulch obtained the highest bulb yields of 7.20 kg/S² (51 tonnes per hectare), followed by the plants without mulch which averaged 4.35 kg/S² (31 tonnes per hectare). The lowest yield has been obtained with the bagged mulch plants, which provided an average of 3.95 kg/S² whether 28 tonnes per hectare.

During the rainy and dry seasons, the variety ARES performed better than the control (variety Karibou). These performances are statically identical during the both seasons. The mass of the bulb fluctuates between 66.60 and 77.82 g while bulb yield varied between 44 and 51 tonnes per hectare. compared to its performances, ARES can be recommended for all season cultivation and extended its cultivation in different agroclimates using rice bran as mulching material.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors thank KAFACI (Korea Africa Food & Agriculture Cooperation Initiative) for funding this study.

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